

ONLINE SUPPLEMENT

URINARY AND PLASMA-DERIVED EXOSOMES REVEAL A DISTINCT MICRORNA SIGNATURE ASSOCIATED WITH ALBUMINURIA IN HYPERTENSION

Running Head: Exosomal miRNA signature associated with albuminuria

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EXPANDED MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research subjects

This is an observational case control study which included essential hypertensive patients with and without persistent elevated urinary albuminuria (≥ 30 mg/g urinary creatinine)¹, such as discovery cohort. A second set of hypertensive patients and a control group of healthy subjects were included as a confirmatory cohort (Figure 1). All hypertensive patients received antihypertensive treatment at the time of the study, and the mean time span of disease progression was five years. Hypertensive patients with severe kidney disease, uncontrolled hypertension, resistant hypertension or secondary hypertension were excluded. Fifteen healthy volunteers were analyzed as a control group without diabetes or hypertension, normal renal function, normal urinalysis, and no history of urinary tract infection, renal stones, or other renal or genitourinary disease.

Therefore, circulating miRNAs in 3 different fractions (total plasma, urinary and plasma-derived exosomes) were assessed by next generation sequencing (NGS) in the discovery cohort and selected miRNA candidates from the dysregulated exo-miRNA profile were subsequently validated by RT-qPCR in the confirmation cohort. The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Clínico Universitario of Valencia in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki of 1975 as revised in 2008. All subjects signed written informed consent.

Urinary albumin excretion

Urinary albumin excretion was measured in first morning urine collections using a nephelometric immunoassay (Behring Institute). For each patient, albuminuria was considered as the mean value obtained from morning spot urine samples and expressed as albumin (mg) / creatinine (mg) ratio (ACR). Increased UAE was defined as ACR ≥ 30 μ g/mg. The coefficient of reproducibility for UAE measurement in our laboratory was intra-assay 2%, inter-assay 6% and intra-individual 12%.

Biological samples

Fresh first morning urinary samples (100 mL) were collected in sterile containers, and human blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes and centrifuged to separate the plasma fraction. All samples were processed within one hour after reception in order to isolate the exosomal component, as explained below.

Exosome isolation

Exosomes were isolated from urine (Exo-U) and plasma (Exo-P) using a protocol based on sequential ultracentrifugation². Briefly, urine samples were initially centrifuged at $2\,250 \times g$ for 30 min to remove cells and debris. Cell-free supernatant was centrifuged at $20\,000 \times g_{av}$ for 45 min to separate large microvesicles. Next, the supernatant was spun at $110,000 \times g_{av}$ in order to obtain the exosome-enriched pellet. After DTT treatment, exosome pellets were washed with PBS, spun again at $110,000 \times g_{av}$ and resuspended in 200 μ l of PBS before storage at -80 °C. For plasma, 2 ml aliquots were diluted 1:4 in filtered PBS and ultracentrifuged similarly, but without DTT treatment. All centrifugations were performed at 4°C using Optima L 100K ultracentrifuge (Beckman Instruments, USA).

Tunable Resistive Pulse Sensing (TRPS)

For single particle analysis, we used the qNano Gold instrument (Izon Science Ltd, New Zealand). Exosome pellets from plasma and urine were diluted 1:100 in PBS, measured using NP150 nanopores and compared to CPC200 calibration beads (mode 203 nm). In both cases, 40 μ L were loaded and at least 500 events were measured for each sample³. Data was recorded using the Izon Control Suite Software version 2.2.2.111. The default minimum blockade height (0.05 nA) for particle detection was used and pressure was set to 1.2 kPa.

Transmission electron microscopy

Approximately 20 μ L of PBS resuspended exosomes were positioned under a formvar/carbon-coated nickel grid for 15 minutes in a dry environment and stained with 2% uranyl acetate for 5 minutes in the dark. Excess liquid was wicked off the grid, and grids were stored at room temperature. Finally, images were obtained with a CM-10 Phillips electron microscope.

Western blot analysis

Total exosome protein was obtained by resuspending exosomes in RIPA lysis buffer containing protease inhibitors and centrifuging at 16 000 x g for 10 minutes afterwards. Total protein amount was calculated by the Lowry method. Approximately 20 μ g of protein from each sample were electrophoresed on 4–12% Bis-Tris NUPAGE SDS-PAGE (Life Technologies, USA) under non-reducing conditions and transferred to a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membrane, blotted with a primary antibody anti-CD9 (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, USA), anti-TSG101, anti-calnexin and anti-GM-130 (Abcam, UK), followed by a secondary IgG Alkaline Phosphatase peroxidase (Sigma, USA). The immunoreactive bands were visualized using nitro blue tetrazolium/5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphate (NBT/BCIP, Sigma, USA) substrate system and quantified using the TotalLab TL-100 (v.2008) program.

RNA extraction

Total RNA was extracted from exosomes using the Total exosome RNA and protein isolation kit (Invitrogen, Life Technologies, US) from 100 μ L of exosome suspension and stored at -80°C. For plasma samples and human podocytes, RNA was obtained using the miRNeasy mini kit (Qiagen, Germany) from 200 μ L of plasma or harvested podocytes, respectively. Quantification of total RNA was performed by NanoDrop ND-1000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, US), whereas quality and size distribution were analyzed by capillary electrophoresis (Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer, Agilent Technologies, USA) with the RNA 6000 Pico chip.

Small RNA library preparation and next-generation sequencing

Single patient libraries were prepared from 2 μ L of total RNA from each condition (total plasma, urinary exosomes or plasma exosomes) using CleanTag Small RNA library preparation kit (TriLink Biotechnologies, US) following an optimized small RNA library preparation protocol to very low input samples previously described⁴. Briefly, after adapter ligation and cDNA amplification containing 1 of 24 index sequences, libraries were size-selected (138–155 bp fragments) on a 15% Novex TBE PAGE gel (Life Technologies, US), purified, re-amplified 10 cycle and quantified by RT-qPCR. Finally, single libraries were normalized to 20 nM prior to be pooled

(24 libraries / pool) and sequenced on the HiSeq 2000 platform (Illumina, US) at 8 pM final concentration with a 50-cycle single read mode (CNAG Barcelona, Spain).

RNA-Seq analysis.

Quality control was carried out using FastQC (v.0.11.4) and the adapters were removed using Cutadapt (v.1.2.1). The mapping was done with Bowtie 2 (v.0.12.7), using the human genome GRCh38. The read count was made by HTSeq and the miRBase database r.21 was used for annotation. Next, we performed the differential expression analysis using edgeR bioconductor package and results were adjusted by age, gender and body mass index. The graphics were made with the ggplot2 and VennDiagram R packages. The raw data are included in the BioProject PRJNA590749 and the corresponding Sequence Read Archive (SRA) and BioSample accession IDs are available in Supplementary Table S1.

KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) pathways over-representation

miRNAs differentially expressed (adjust p-value < 0.05 and absolute \log_2 fold-change ≥ 2) were included in the KEGG pathways over-representation analysis, using the miEAA tool, and only the pathways related to the HTN and kidney damage were considered. In addition, the mRNA targets for the experimentally validated miRNAs were predicted using TargetScan, DIANA tools and mirDB. Only the miRNA-mRNA target with the highest prediction values and common to all methods were included. The proteins coded by the mRNA target that belonged to the over-represented KEGG pathways were identified using KEGG database. Finally, protein-protein interaction was obtained from STRING (Search Tool for the Retrieval of Interacting Genes/Proteins) database and the networks were analyzed using Cytoscape V.3.7.1.

RT-q PCR validation of exosome miRNAs

To validate RNAseq data, we performed RT-qPCR analysis of selected exo-miRNAs using TaqMan™ Advanced miRNA assays (Applied Biosystems, USA). MiRNA selection criteria for NGS data included presence in at least 75% of samples in both study groups, and an absolute \log_2 FC ≥ 2 . In addition, priority was given to circulating miRNAs previously related to renal injury and/or presenting cell-specific expression in the kidney⁵. Briefly, 2 μ L of total RNA were retrotranscribed to cDNA using the TaqMan advanced miRNA cDNA synthesis kit. Diluted cDNA was combined with 2X Advanced TaqMan Master Mix II and specific TaqMan miRNA probes (Supplementary Table S2). All reactions were run in triplicate, including blank/negative controls without cDNA, and were performed using the LightCycler 480 II real-time PCR system (Roche). Data was analyzed with LightCycler 480 software (v1.5). Absolute copy number for each target miRNA was calculated using a standard curve prepared with a synthetic miRNA (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) in a range from 10^{10} to 10^2 copies. Due to the absence of validated reference genes to measure exosomal miRNA expression data, we selected two miRNAs as internal controls of our experiment (miR-125a and miR-186) due to their stable expression across fractions (total plasma, urinary exosomes, plasma exosomes). MiRNA values were expressed as the log ratio between the values of miRNAs of interest and the average value of internal control miRNAs.

Podocyte culture

Conditionally immortalized human podocytes were developed by transfection with the temperature-sensitive SV40 T-gene, as previously described⁶. In brief, cells were cultured under growth-permissive conditions at 33°C in RPMI 1640 medium (Biowest, France) supplemented with 10% exosome-depleted fetal bovine serum (FBS; Biowest, France) and insulin–transferrin–selenite supplement (Sigma-Aldrich, US). For differentiation, podocytes were maintained under non-permissive conditions at 37.6°C for 10 days with 2% FBS, prior to the experiments. Cells were made quiescent in RPMI 1640 medium with 0% FBS for 24 h before stimulation with recombinant human TGF- β 1 (Sigma-Aldrich, US) at several concentrations (5 ng/ml, 10 ng/mL and 15 ng/mL) for up to 24 h to assess miR-26a changes in exosomal and cellular fractions. Conditioned media (45 mL) were collected and processed for exosome isolation as indicated above and cells were harvested for total RNA extraction.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism software (GraphPad, US) and SPSS software (SPSS, US). Results for each variable were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method. Clinical variables were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation or percentage. Comparisons between groups for the categorical variables were performed with the Chi-square test and the T-student's test for continuous variables. In dot plot images, horizontal lines represent the median and interquartile ranges. Mann-Whitney U-test was used to determine significant differences in exosomal miRNA levels among patient groups and for human podocytes experiments. Finally, Spearman's correlation coefficient was used to determine the association between exosomal miRNA levels and UAE. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

SUPPLEMENTAL REFERENCE SECTION

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Table S1. SRA_BioProject_ID. The raw data are included in the BioProject PRJNA590749 and the corresponding Sequence Read Archive (SRA) and BioSample accession IDs. (An excel file)

Table S2. List of TaqMan Advanced probes used in the present study.

miRNA ID	miRbase Accession Number	TaqMan Advanced Probe
hsa-miR-126-3p	MIMAT0000445	477887_mir
hsa-miR-143-3p	MIMAT0000435	477912_mir
hsa-miR-144-3p	MIMAT0000436	477913_mir
hsa-miR-191-5p	MIMAT0000440	477952_mir
hsa-miR-200a-3p	MIMAT0000682	478490_mir
hsa-miR-222-3p	MIMAT0000279	477982_mir
hsa-miR-26a-5p	MIMAT0000082	477995_mir
hsa-miR-423-5p	MIMAT0004748	478090_mir

Table S3. Clinical characteristics of the confirmation cohort.

Variables	Albuminuria (UAE) (n = 39)	Normoalbuminuria (Non UAE) (n = 30)
Age (years)	58.0 ± 11.2	54.6 ± 5.6
Gender (male)	70.6 %	64.6 %
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	138 ± 19	134 ± 24
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	83 ± 11	88 ± 15
Pulse pressure (mmHg)	54 ± 15	48 ± 6
Glucose (mg/dL)	130 ± 51	118 ± 40
Glycated hemoglobin (%)	6.9 ± 1.2	6.1 ± 0.8
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	190 ± 35*	174 ± 28
LDL (mg/dL)	120 ± 31*	109 ± 23
HDL (mg/dL)	47 ± 13	49 ± 11
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	171 ± 114	129 ± 59
Plasma creatinine (mg/dL)	1.0 ± 0.38	0.89 ± 0.21
Glomerular filtration rate (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	86 ± 30	88 ± 19
Waist (cm)	108 ± 12	99 ± 12
Central obesity (%)	78	82
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	33 ± 7	30 ± 6
Obesity (%)	56	41
Obesity grade (%)		
Grade I	22	19
Grade II	22	11
Grade III	12	11
Diabetes (%)	43	32
Dyslipidemia (%)	92	82
Smoking (%)	38	48
Ex-Smoking (%)	32	14
Urinary albumin excretion/Creatinine (mg/g)	216.1 ± 196.2†	3.4 ± 2.3
Antihypertensive treatment (%)		
ARB	90	93
CCB	38	32
Diuretics	64	64
Statins	36	10

Data are expressed as mean ± SD, unless otherwise noted. Glomerular filtration rate calculated by MDRD formula. Comparisons between groups: * p < 0.01, † p < 0.001. ARB: angiotensin II receptor antagonists; CCB: calcium channel blocker. HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, high-density lipoprotein.

Table S4. Differentially expressed miRNAs in UAE vs Non UAE.

Up-regulated miRNAs				
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-664a-3p	2.76	Plasma	0.0002	0.0701
hsa-miR-376c-3p	2.62	Plasma	0.0011	0.1509
hsa-miR-154-3p	2.62	Plasma	0.0015	0.1509
hsa-miR-374a-5p	2.58	Plasma	2.71E-05	0.0164
hsa-miR-1260b	2.55	Plasma	0.0061	0.1948
hsa-miR-548e-3p	2.36	Plasma	0.0094	0.2553
hsa-miR-486-3p	2.34	Plasma	0.0027	0.1611
hsa-miR-337-3p	2.30	Plasma	0.0261	0.3098
hsa-miR-3161	2.26	Plasma	0.0163	0.2739
hsa-miR-548ax	2.24	Plasma	0.0247	0.3054
hsa-miR-5584-5p	2.21	Plasma	0.0027	0.1611
hsa-miR-411-3p	1.92	Plasma	0.0053	0.1906
hsa-miR-654-3p	1.90	Plasma	0.0022	0.1611
hsa-miR-4781-3p	1.87	Plasma	0.0499	0.3953
hsa-miR-23b-3p	1.85	Plasma	0.0006	0.1165
hsa-let-7a-5p	1.77	Plasma	0.0047	0.1906
hsa-miR-6758-5p	1.73	Plasma	0.0130	0.2553
hsa-miR-199a-3p	1.68	Plasma	0.0188	0.2876
hsa-miR-224-5p	1.67	Plasma	0.0140	0.2553
hsa-miR-6825-5p	1.61	Plasma	0.0044	0.1906
hsa-miR-5090	1.60	Plasma	0.0047	0.1906
hsa-miR-486-5p	1.56	Plasma	0.0015	0.1509
hsa-miR-651-5p	1.54	Plasma	0.0297	0.3335
hsa-miR-539-5p	1.46	Plasma	0.0122	0.2553
hsa-miR-628-5p	1.44	Plasma	0.0234	0.3000
hsa-miR-556-5p	1.44	Plasma	0.0391	0.3496
hsa-miR-19a-3p	1.43	Plasma	0.0061	0.1948
hsa-miR-4667-5p	1.42	Plasma	0.0278	0.3242
hsa-miR-4775	1.39	Plasma	0.0353	0.3496
hsa-miR-106b-3p	1.35	Plasma	0.0041	0.1906
hsa-miR-18a-5p	1.34	Plasma	0.0289	0.3310
hsa-miR-151a-5p	1.34	Plasma	0.0131	0.2553
hsa-miR-625-5p	1.32	Plasma	0.0401	0.3496
hsa-miR-4511	1.30	Plasma	0.0386	0.3496
hsa-miR-195-5p	1.30	Plasma	0.0321	0.3426
hsa-miR-6513-3p	1.28	Plasma	0.0409	0.3496
hsa-miR-28-5p	1.27	Plasma	0.0224	0.3000
hsa-miR-6516-5p	1.27	Plasma	0.0192	0.2876
hsa-miR-301a-3p	1.26	Plasma	0.0097	0.2553
hsa-let-7e-5p	1.25	Plasma	0.0118	0.2553

hsa-miR-4446-3p	1.25	Plasma	0.0143	0.2553
hsa-miR-93-5p	1.14	Plasma	0.0029	0.1611
hsa-miR-493-5p	1.11	Plasma	0.0103	0.2553
hsa-miR-3605-5p	1.11	Plasma	0.0195	0.2876
hsa-miR-3138	1.09	Plasma	0.0234	0.3000
hsa-miR-1307-3p	1.09	Plasma	0.0129	0.2553
hsa-miR-99b-3p	1.09	Plasma	0.0455	0.3760
hsa-miR-320a	1.07	Plasma	0.0025	0.1611
hsa-miR-5187-5p	1.05	Plasma	0.0128	0.2553
hsa-miR-99b-5p	0.99	Plasma	0.0225	0.3000
hsa-miR-3154	0.97	Plasma	0.0421	0.3547
hsa-miR-27a-3p	0.95	Plasma	0.0238	0.3000
hsa-let-7i-5p	0.94	Plasma	0.0140	0.2553
hsa-miR-744-5p	0.94	Plasma	0.0182	0.2876
hsa-miR-939-5p	0.93	Plasma	0.0053	0.1906
hsa-let-7d-5p	0.92	Plasma	0.0143	0.2553
hsa-miR-32-3p	0.90	Plasma	0.0409	0.3496
hsa-miR-200c-3p	0.89	Plasma	0.0185	0.2876
hsa-miR-889-3p	0.89	Plasma	0.0334	0.3426
hsa-miR-126-3p	0.89	Plasma	0.0260	0.3098
hsa-let-7b-5p	0.88	Plasma	0.0065	0.1980
hsa-miR-664a-5p	0.87	Plasma	0.0459	0.3760
hsa-let-7f-5p	0.86	Plasma	0.0217	0.3000
hsa-miR-98-5p	0.80	Plasma	0.0384	0.3496
hsa-miR-548l	0.73	Plasma	0.0386	0.3496
hsa-let-7g-5p	0.72	Plasma	0.0322	0.3426
hsa-let-7c-5p	0.63	Plasma	0.0129	0.2553
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-23b-3p	6.07	Exosome Plasma	6.28E-05	0.0110
hsa-let-7e-5p	4.85	Exosome Plasma	1.38E-05	0.0056
hsa-miR-144-3p	4.42	Exosome Plasma	0.0090	0.1701
hsa-miR-142-5p	4.28	Exosome Plasma	0.0001	0.0110
hsa-miR-363-3p	4.13	Exosome Plasma	0.0096	0.1701
hsa-let-7d-3p	4.06	Exosome Plasma	0.0004	0.0300
hsa-miR-126-3p	3.85	Exosome Plasma	0.0013	0.0672
hsa-miR-654-3p	3.64	Exosome Plasma	0.0005	0.0309
hsa-miR-223-3p	3.44	Exosome Plasma	0.0070	0.1701
hsa-let-7d-5p	3.25	Exosome Plasma	0.0003	0.0300
hsa-miR-126-5p	3.19	Exosome Plasma	0.0021	0.0716
hsa-let-7g-5p	2.87	Exosome Plasma	0.0007	0.0419
hsa-miR-122-5p	2.82	Exosome Plasma	0.0348	0.2401
hsa-miR-23a-3p	2.72	Exosome Plasma	0.0090	0.1701
hsa-miR-627-5p	2.62	Exosome Plasma	0.0472	0.2685
hsa-miR-26b-5p	2.39	Exosome Plasma	0.0021	0.0716

hsa-miR-191-5p	2.09	Exosome Plasma	0.0071	0.1701
hsa-miR-151a-3p	2.02	Exosome Plasma	0.0164	0.1991
hsa-let-7f-5p	1.89	Exosome Plasma	0.0074	0.1701
hsa-miR-423-5p	1.84	Exosome Plasma	0.0161	0.1991
hsa-miR-425-5p	1.80	Exosome Plasma	0.0169	0.1991
hsa-let-7b-5p	1.60	Exosome Plasma	0.0125	0.1878
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-934	5.47	Exosome Urine	0.0048	0.4881
hsa-miR-7706	3.57	Exosome Urine	0.0122	0.5549
hsa-miR-143-3p	2.06	Exosome Urine	0.0336	0.9795
hsa-let-7e-5p	0.88	Exosome Urine	0.0028	0.4881
hsa-miR-99b-5p	0.76	Exosome Urine	0.0364	0.9795
hsa-miR-92b-3p	0.68	Exosome Urine	0.0467	0.9795
Down-regulated miRNAs				
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-4796-5p	-1.90	Plasma	0.0389	0.3496
hsa-miR-2116-3p	-1.88	Plasma	0.0410	0.3496
hsa-miR-3143	-1.44	Plasma	0.0339	0.3426
hsa-miR-3176	-1.31	Plasma	0.0379	0.3496
hsa-miR-500a-3p	-1.27	Plasma	0.0163	0.2739
hsa-miR-221-5p	-1.12	Plasma	0.0199	0.2876
hsa-miR-136-3p	-1.01	Plasma	0.0468	0.3780
hsa-miR-758-3p	-0.92	Plasma	0.0328	0.3426
hsa-miR-1307-5p	-0.77	Plasma	0.0314	0.3426
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-200b-3p	-6.51	Exosome Plasma	0.0019	0.0716
hsa-miR-31-5p	-5.53	Exosome Plasma	0.0051	0.1473
hsa-miR-194-5p	-4.57	Exosome Plasma	0.0231	0.2137
hsa-miR-6837-3p	-4.24	Exosome Plasma	0.0200	0.2066
hsa-miR-429	-4.21	Exosome Plasma	0.0424	0.2604
hsa-miR-409-5p	-3.97	Exosome Plasma	0.0083	0.1701
hsa-miR-204-5p	-3.62	Exosome Plasma	0.0333	0.2401
hsa-miR-504-5p	-3.60	Exosome Plasma	0.0244	0.2207
hsa-miR-7-5p	-3.55	Exosome Plasma	0.0096	0.1701
hsa-miR-99b-3p	-3.51	Exosome Plasma	0.0192	0.2055
hsa-miR-2467-5p	-3.50	Exosome Plasma	0.0261	0.2257
hsa-miR-200a-3p	-3.48	Exosome Plasma	0.0152	0.1991
hsa-miR-125b-2-3p	-3.44	Exosome Plasma	0.0090	0.1701
hsa-miR-412-5p	-3.38	Exosome Plasma	0.0432	0.2604
hsa-miR-34a-5p	-3.30	Exosome Plasma	0.0319	0.2401
hsa-miR-539-3p	-3.29	Exosome Plasma	0.0152	0.1991
hsa-miR-375	-3.28	Exosome Plasma	0.0019	0.0716
hsa-miR-656-3p	-3.28	Exosome Plasma	0.0391	0.2535

hsa-miR-203a-3p	-3.18	Exosome Plasma	0.0252	0.2231
hsa-miR-500a-3p	-3.13	Exosome Plasma	0.0440	0.2604
hsa-miR-452-5p	-3.13	Exosome Plasma	0.0344	0.2401
hsa-miR-103a-3p	-3.13	Exosome Plasma	0.0347	0.2401
hsa-miR-337-5p	-3.12	Exosome Plasma	0.0438	0.2604
hsa-miR-190b	-3.09	Exosome Plasma	0.0212	0.2066
hsa-miR-141-3p	-3.02	Exosome Plasma	0.0217	0.2066
hsa-miR-30a-3p	-3.00	Exosome Plasma	0.0322	0.2401
hsa-miR-1306-3p	-3.00	Exosome Plasma	0.0474	0.2685
hsa-miR-199b-5p	-2.91	Exosome Plasma	0.0417	0.2604
hsa-miR-92a-1-5p	-2.91	Exosome Plasma	0.0487	0.2685
hsa-miR-1185-1-3p	-2.85	Exosome Plasma	0.0317	0.2401
hsa-miR-1270	-2.83	Exosome Plasma	0.0441	0.2604
hsa-miR-1185-2-3p	-2.80	Exosome Plasma	0.0274	0.2323
hsa-miR-326	-2.78	Exosome Plasma	0.0281	0.2336
hsa-miR-6816-3p	-2.76	Exosome Plasma	0.0489	0.2685
hsa-miR-598-3p	-2.74	Exosome Plasma	0.0317	0.2401
hsa-miR-3613-5p	-2.66	Exosome Plasma	0.0392	0.2535
hsa-miR-30a-5p	-2.57	Exosome Plasma	0.0136	0.1984
hsa-miR-98-3p	-2.50	Exosome Plasma	0.0346	0.2401
hsa-miR-381-3p	-2.36	Exosome Plasma	0.0118	0.1850
hsa-miR-148b-5p	-2.35	Exosome Plasma	0.0181	0.2040
hsa-miR-191-3p	-2.35	Exosome Plasma	0.0384	0.2535
hsa-miR-6852-5p	-2.28	Exosome Plasma	0.0218	0.2066
hsa-miR-181a-2-3p	-2.18	Exosome Plasma	0.0165	0.1991
hsa-miR-222-3p	-2.16	Exosome Plasma	0.0023	0.0720
hsa-miR-140-5p	-2.15	Exosome Plasma	0.0185	0.2040
hsa-miR-99a-5p	-2.01	Exosome Plasma	0.0495	0.2685
hsa-miR-30e-3p	-2.01	Exosome Plasma	0.0116	0.1850
hsa-miR-370-3p	-2.01	Exosome Plasma	0.0307	0.2401
hsa-miR-340-5p	-1.89	Exosome Plasma	0.0104	0.1758
hsa-miR-26a-5p	-1.82	Exosome Plasma	0.0171	0.1991
hsa-miR-107	-1.70	Exosome Plasma	0.0217	0.2066
hsa-miR-345-5p	-1.56	Exosome Plasma	0.0492	0.2685
hsa-miR-140-3p	-1.40	Exosome Plasma	0.0386	0.2535
miRNA	log₂ FC	Biofluid	p-value	FDR
hsa-miR-26a-5p	-2.02	Exosome Urine	0.0086	0.4881
hsa-miR-146a-5p	-1.35	Exosome Urine	0.0081	0.4881

FC: Fold change; FDR: False discovery rate

Figure S1. Characterization of urinary and plasma exosomes isolated by ultracentrifugation. Electron microscopy (EM) micrographs of negative-stained extracellular vesicles. A) Exosome pellets from urine (left) and plasma (right) of hypertensive patients were analyzed by electron microscopy and tunable resistive pulse sensing (TRPS). Micrographs of negative-stained vesicles and representative size distribution and concentration measured by TRPS are shown. Size bar represents 100 nm. B) Capillary electrophoresis profile of exosomal RNA from urine (up) and plasma (down) confirmed enrichment in the small RNA fraction. C) Identification of exosomal markers (Tsg101 and CD9) by Western blotting. Whole-cell lysates from HuH7 cells were loaded as a positive control. Exo_U: urinary exosomes; Exo_P: plasma exosomes; UAE: Urinary albumin excretion.

Figure S2. RT-qPCR analysis of exosomal miRNAs in the confirmation cohort. No significant changes were found in the amount of plasma exo-miR-144-3p (A), miR-200a-3p (B) or miR-423-5p (C) between CNT or hypertensive patients with (UAE) or without UAE (Non UAE). Absolute copy number was normalized to miR-125a and miR-186 internal controls. Data was compared using Mann-Whitney U-test. CNT: healthy controls; P-Exo: plasma exosomes; UAE: urinary albumin excretion; U-Exo: urinary exosomes